

An observation metamodel for dependability tools: technical report

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Abstract—In this technical report, we illustrate the extension of the FaultFlow library [7] with an observation metamodel [1], referring to a case study from the literature on floating offshore wind turbines [12]. Specifically, first we describe the structure and failure logic of the considered system and we extend it with two realistic observation mechanisms (Section I); then, we present the instance of the extended FaultFlow metamodel that represents structure, failure logic, and observation mechanisms of the system (Section II); and, finally, we illustrate translation of the metamodel instance into a Stochastic Time Petri Net (STPN) representing failure logic and observation mechanisms (Section III).

Index Terms—Systems of Systems, dependability evaluation, Model-Driven Engineering, software tools and libraries.

I. THE FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND TURBINE CASE STUDY

We consider the Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOTW) system of [12], where the system structure is described through a systematic grading, and its failure logic is defined in terms of SFTs by identifying occurrence rates of basic events based on previous studies, databases collecting data on systems actually in operation, and annual industrial reports [2], [10]. In particular, we focus on the semi-floating foundation subsystem of the FOWT, providing a SysML Block Definition Diagram (BDD) [5] describing the subsystem structure and a Stochastic Fault Tree (SFT) characterizing its failure, extended to account also for duration of fault propagations.

Fig. 1(a) shows the SysML BDD modeling the structure of the semi-floating foundation subsystem. The subsystem consists of the floating structure, responsible for keeping the entire FOWT system stable and afloat, and the mooring system, responsible for keeping the floating structure in position. In turn, the floating structure is made of columns, ensuring stabilized buoyancy and held together by diagonal bracing, and the mooring system is made of mooring lines and anchors.

Fig. 1(b) shows the SFT of the “semi-floating foundation failure” (F), extended with durations of fault propagations. Specifically, the top event can be caused by the basic events “pillar damage” (F1) or “capsize” (F9), or by the non-basic events “water tightness error” and “hit by dropped objects”. In turn, “water tightness error” is triggered if both the basic event “insufficient detection” (F5) and the non-basic event “pipe joint failure” happen. Moreover, “pipe joint failure” occurs

Fig. 1. Semi-Floating Foundation of the FOWT system [12]: (a) SysML BDD defining the system structure and (b) SFT defining the system failure logic (extended with duration of fault propagations). Time is expressed in h.

if the basic events “corrosion of pipe joint” (F2), “weld defect of pipe joint” (F3), and “fatigue of pipe joint” (F4) occur. Furthermore, “hit by dropped objects” is triggered by things falling over the considered subsystem, such as “biologics” (F8)

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or “planes” (F7) or “objects brought by a typhoon” (F6).

Basic events F1, F2, . . . , F9 are characterized by Exponential time-to-occurrence as defined in [12]. This assumption is justified in [12] by the fact that failure data are taken from the OREDA database [4], which collects data on reliability and maintainability of industrial components in the oil & gas sector, primarily offshore subsea and topside equipments. Given that these components are frequently subject to maintenance or replacement, they are typically replaced or refurbished before reaching their wear-out phase. Therefore, failure events are likely to occur during their useful life phase, and thus failure rates can be considered time-independent, i.e., constant.

Conversely, duration of fault propagations typically takes a non-Exponential distribution with bounded support. Among non-Exponential distributions, FaultFlow supports expolynomial functions, also termed expomials [9]), which are defined as the sum of products of Exponential and polynomial terms, i.e., $f(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} c_m \prod_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n^{\alpha_{mn}} e^{-\lambda_{mn} x_n}$, and they either have analytical representation over their domain or are piecewise-defined over multiple sub-domains. Expomials facilitate fitting of analytical Probability Density Functions (PDFs) from duration statistics, and are supported by the ORIS tool [6] and its Sirio library [8] which we use for translation of FaultFlow metamodel instances into Stochastic Time Petri Nets (STPNs) [11] and for their subsequent analysis. For the case study considered in this report, we assume that propagation from the conjunction of F2, F3, and F4 to “pipe joint failure” takes a duration within interval $[a, b]$ and lower than $c \in (a, b)$ with probability p , with $a = 0$ h, $b = 24$ h, $c = 18$ h, and $p = 0.75$. This statistics is fit by an expolynomial PDF $f(x) = \alpha (x - a) (b - x) e^{-\lambda x}$ with $\alpha, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$ such that $\int_a^b f(x) dx = 1$ and $\int_a^c f(x) dx = p$, preserving finite support with null values at the borders and integral over $[a, c]$ equal to p . In particular, we obtain $\alpha = 0.000187563$ and $\lambda = -0.0649042$. Similarly, we assume that propagation from the conjunction of “pipe joint failure” and F5 to “water tightness error” takes a duration within $[0, 72]$ h and lower than 24 h with probability 0.5, which is fit by the already defined PDF $f(x)$, with $a = 0$ h, $a = 72$ h, $\alpha = 0.000056409$, and $\lambda = 0.0406479$. We also consider that propagation from F6, or F7, or F8 to “hit by dropped objects” takes a zero time, and that propagation from F1, or “water tightness error”, or “hit by dropped objects, or F9 to F takes a uniform PDF over $[0, 6]$ h. It is worth noting that any other distribution in the class of expolynomial functions could be considered as well.

Finally, according to the observation metamodel defined for the FaultFlow library in [1], we consider two realistic observation processes for the semi-floating foundation of the FOWT system. Specifically, based on conclusions drawn in [12], we consider that operation of the diagonal bracing component (i.e., DiagonalBracing block in the BDD of Fig. 1(a)) is checked to schedule maintenance upon a failure occurs. We also consider the case that the floating structure (i.e., FloatingStructure block in the BDD of Fig. 1(a)) is equipped with a level sensor that recurrently monitors the water level housed within the structure, to support generation

of appropriate alerts to users as soon as the water level exceeds given thresholds. It is worth noting that similar observation processes could be defined for other components of the semi-floating foundation, as well as multiple observation policies could be defined also for the same component.

II. REPRESENTATION IN FAULTFLOW

Fig. 2 shows the instance of the FaultFlow metamodel that defines the structure, failure logic, and observation processes of the semi-floating foundation of the FOWT. FaultFlow [3] supports automated derivation of the portions of metamodel instances defining the structure and failure logic of an SoS from SysML BDDs and SFTs, respectively, while the observation metamodel and the related Model-to-Model (M2M) transformations are currently under development.

Specifically, in the bottom part of the diagram of Fig. 2, objects having blue scale background define the hierarchical structure of the semi-floating foundation, with a one-to-one mapping between blocks of the SysML BDD of Fig. 1(a) and ComponentType instances. In particular, note that object semiFloatingFoundation accounts for one of the components (i.e., components[0]) of object FOWTSystem which, in turn, models the entire FOWT system.

In the top part of the diagram of Fig. 2, objects having orange scale background define the failure logic of the semi-floating foundation, with basic events in the SFT of Fig. 1(b) corresponding to InternalFaultMode instances, and non-basic events corresponding to PropagationPortType instances. In particular, note that object semiFloatingFoundationFailure models the top event of the entire SFT.

In the bottom part of the diagram of Fig. 2, objects having yellow scale background define the observation processes of the semi-floating foundation. Specifically, diagonal bracing maintenance upon failure is represented by object diagonalBracingOP of class ObservationPortType, connected with object jointMaintenanceCheck of class ObservationType and with object diagonalBracing of class ComponentType. Each concrete maintenance is then modeled by an object of class CategoryObservation like concreteMaintenanceCheck, associated with object jointMaintenanceCheck and modeling a qualitative observation (object maintenance of class Category) on condition of joints (object jointCondition of class PhenomenonType).

Moreover, recurrent monitoring of the water level within the structure is represented by object floatingStructureOP of class ObservationPortType, connected with object waterLevelObservation of class ObservationType and with object floatingStructure of class ComponentType. Each concrete maintenance is then modeled by an object of class Measurement like levelSensorMeasurement, associated with object waterLevelObservation and modeling a quantitative observation (object quantityMeasured of class Quantity) on water level (object waterLevel of class PhenomenonType) expressed in liters (object liter of class Unit).

Fig. 2. Instance of the extended Fault Flow metamodel, representing the structure (blue scale background objects) and failure logic (orange scale background objects) of the semi-floating foundation of the FOWT system [12], here extended with two observation policies (yellow scale background objects).

III. TRANSLATION INTO STPN

The FaultFlow metamodel instance of Fig. 2 can be translated into a Sirio metamodel instance, comprising an STPN that represents the failure logic and the observation processes of the considered case study, as illustrated in [1]. FaultFlow [3] supports automated translation of the portions of metamodel instances defining the structure and failure logic of an SoS into

an STPN, while automated translation of the portion defining observation processes is currently under development.

According to the transformation rules presented in [1], transitions $F1_Occurrence$, $F2_Occurrence$, ..., $F9_Occurrence$ model the time-to-fault duration distribution of faults F1, F2, ..., F9, respectively. Transitions $pipeJointError_Occurrence$, $droppedObjectError_Occurrence$, and $waterTightnessError_Occurrence$

Fig. 3. STPN modeling failure logic and observation processes of the system shown in Fig. 2. White and black thick bars represent transitions with Exponential and non-Exponential time-to-fire distribution, respectively. Black thin bars represent transitions with zero time-to-fire.

currence model the fault-to-failure propagations for the diagonal bracing, the floating structure, and the mooring system, respectively, and transitions `pipeJointFailure_to_fsFault`, `droppedObjectHit_to_dsffFault`, and `waterTightnessFailure_to_wsffFault` represent the subsequent immediate occurrence of an external fault for the floating structure, the semi-floating foundation, and the semi-floating foundation, respectively. Finally, transition `SemiFloatingFoundationFailure_Occurrence` models the semi-floating foundation failure.

Finally, transition `FailureObservation` models the immediate detection of a pipe joint failure of the diagonal bracing, while transition `waterLevelObservation` with deterministic time-to-fire represents recurrent monitoring of the water level of the floating structure. Both transitions have an entry-point function returning the observation value (e.g., a binary value encoding whether a pipe joint failure has occurred or not) based on the state of the observed component (e.g., faults, errors and failure of the diagonal bracing). We are extending the implementation of the STPN simulator of Sirio to use such entry-point functions to generate time-stamped observations of the system behavior during simulation.

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